

An Empirical Study in Singapore to Understand Public Acceptance of Using Artificial Intelligence (AI) Diagnosis to Make Treatment Recommendations

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly integrated into clinical decision-making, yet public acceptance remains uncertain, particularly in high-stakes healthcare contexts. This study examines factors influencing acceptance of AI-driven diagnosis and treatment recommendations among the Singapore public. Drawing on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology, Trust in Automation Theory and Perceived Risk Theory, it investigates performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, trust in AI, and perceived risk in shaping behavioural intention. A quantitative survey of 108 respondents was conducted, and data were analysed using descriptive statistics and Spearman correlation tests.

The findings show that all constructs were significantly associated with acceptance. Trust was the strongest predictor, followed by performance expectancy, while perceived risk showed a substantial negative relationship with behavioural intention. Effort expectancy and social influence exerted moderate but meaningful effects. Acceptance of medical AI is shaped not only by perceived usefulness but also by reassurance, transparency, and clinician involvement. These factors are especially relevant in Singapore's high-trust, risk-averse healthcare environment.

The study advances understanding by integrating trust and perceived risk into a UTAUT-based model and providing context-specific insights for Singapore. Recommendations include enhancing explainability, improving public education, strengthening regulatory assurance, and conducting research involving healthcare professionals and high-stakes scenarios. Overall, the study underscores the importance of human-centred, transparent and ethically governed AI in healthcare.

Key Words : Artificial Intelligence (AI); Medical AI; AI Diagnosis; Technology Acceptance; UTAUT; Trust in Automation; Perceived Risk; Behavioural Intention; Public Acceptance; Explainable AI (XAI); Healthcare Technology; Singapore Healthcare

Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Research Background and Significance

1.1.1 Background

The healthcare sector is experiencing increasing pressure as population growth and demographic shifts elevate the demand for high-quality medical services. In Singapore, this demand is further intensified by rising life expectancy and a rapidly ageing population. Both of which contribute to greater utilisation of healthcare resources. These developments have placed substantial strain on the healthcare system, leading to persistent shortages of skilled healthcare workers (Chua, 2020). Workforce shortages, in turn increase the workload of existing professionals and heighten the risk of adverse clinical outcomes including diagnostic errors. Misdiagnosis is often preventable and can lead to severe harm or death, addressing diagnostic errors is an essential priority for ensuring patient safety in healthcare (Newman-Toker, 2025).

These systemic pressures underscore the need for innovative solutions that can support clinical decision-making and enhance the efficiency of healthcare delivery. The emergence of AI in medical diagnosis presents a potential avenue to address these challenges by reducing clinician workload, improving diagnostic accuracy and supporting timely treatment recommendations (D'Adderio and Bates, 2025). However, despite its potential benefits, the adoption of AI-driven diagnostic tools ultimately depends on the public's willingness to trust and accept such technologies.

1.1.2 Significance

This study makes a meaningful contribution to the understanding of medical AI adoption by extending existing technology-acceptance models through the integration of the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), Trust in Automation Theory and Perceived Risk Theory. This framework offers a more comprehensive explanation of how cognitive evaluations, trust dynamics and risk perceptions shape public attitudes toward AI-driven diagnosis. By focusing specifically on the Singapore public, the study provides context-sensitive insights that reflect the country's distinctive healthcare culture characterised by high institutional trust and risk-averse decision-making.

The findings generate practical implications for policymakers, healthcare institutions, and AI developers by identifying key levers such as trust, performance expectancy and risk mitigation that must be prioritised for effective and responsible AI implementation. Moreover, the study provides timely baseline evidence at an early stage of AI integration in Singapore, offering a valuable foundation for future longitudinal and comparative research examining how acceptance evolves as AI becomes increasingly embedded in clinical practice.

1.2 Research Questions and Methods

This study aims to examine how members of the Singapore public evaluate and accept the use of AI-driven diagnosis and treatment recommendations. Guided by the integrated theoretical framework combining UTAUT, Trust in Automation Theory, and Perceived Risk Theory. The study is structured around the following research question:

Main Research Question

What factors influence public acceptance of AI diagnosis for treatment recommendations in Singapore?

To provide a more detailed examination of the determinants of acceptance is supported by the following sub-questions, each aligned with the study's five theoretical constructs:

- **RQ1:** How does performance expectancy influence acceptance of AI diagnosis for treatment recommendation?
- **RQ2:** How does effort expectancy influence acceptance of AI diagnosis for treatment recommendations?
- **RQ3:** How does social influence shape acceptance of medical AI?
- **RQ4:** How does trust and perceived risk in AI affect behavioural intention to rely on AI diagnosis for treatment recommendations?

These research questions directly inform the hypotheses and structure of the empirical analysis presented in Chapters 4, 5, and 6.

1.3 Research Gaps

The emergence of AI had been touted as the fourth industrial revolution. Although it is still in its infancy, this technology is promising and there is potential for commercialization. AI is expected to generate predictions that are more efficient, more accurate and more cost-effective, while also influencing complementary activities such as decision-making, data collection and human judgment (Velarde, 2019). As such, AI can be applied into the healthcare industry to improve better patient outcomes.

First, AI-driven diagnosis is still a novel and complex technology, and the public often lacks sufficient understanding of how such systems operate. This limited awareness can heighten uncertainty, thereby influencing key psychological determinants such as trust and perceived risk. As a result, public acceptance of AI-based diagnostic recommendations may be shaped more by misconceptions or fear than by evidence of clinical performance. AI-driven healthcare could boost equity in health results, lower diagnostic mistakes, enhance treatment methods and potentially alleviate the growing workforce shortages in health providers (Witkowski, Okhai and Neely, 2024). It is important to note that AI still at its infancy and more time will be needed to assess its reliability in the healthcare industry.

Secondly, UTAUT is widely used to explain technology adoption, it does not explicitly incorporate constructs related to trust or perceived risk. These factors are particularly critical in healthcare settings, where the consequences of technology failure such as diagnostic errors can be severe and potentially life-threatening (Abe et al., 2019). Therefore, relying solely on UTAUT without integrating these additional constructs produces a theoretical gap. The model may insufficiently explain public acceptance of AI systems that directly influence medical outcomes. This limitation highlights the need for extended frameworks that captures trust and perceived risk as central determinants of acceptance. In rare cases, some people are willing to

accept new technology without trusting it, so it is crucial to note that there might a possibility that the acceptance is not affected by trust (Shevtsova et al., 2024).

Lastly, most existing studies on AI adoption in healthcare are conducted primarily from the perspectives of physicians, medical specialists or administrators. Far fewer investigations consider the viewpoints of developers, healthcare institutions, regulators or the public who are ultimately the end users and recipients of AI-supported clinical recommendations. This omission creates a significant stakeholder gap in the literature. In addition, much of the available empirical evidence is derived from Western healthcare systems, which differ substantially from Asian contexts in areas such as technology readiness, cultural attitudes toward risk, trust in medical institutions and expectations of care delivery. Consequently, findings from Western settings may not be directly applicable to Singapore, highlighting both geographical and cultural gaps. These limitations underscore the need for research that examines AI diagnostic acceptance within Asian populations and incorporates a broader, more diverse set of stakeholder perspectives.

Taken together, these three gaps demonstrate that existing research insufficiently accounts for the public's limited understanding of AI and its influence on trust and risk perceptions. The theoretical shortcomings of UTAUT in high-severity clinical applications and the narrow focus on physicians and Western contexts. Addressing these gaps is essential to developing a more holistic understanding of how the public evaluates and accepts AI-driven diagnostic and treatment recommendations in Singapore.

Chapter 2 Theoretical Framework and Literature review

Overview

This chapter establishes the theoretical and empirical foundations for examining public acceptance of AI-driven diagnosis in Singapore. It introduces the integrated framework combining UTAUT, Trust in Automation theory, and Perceived Risk theory. The chapter then synthesises current evidence on AI in healthcare, public perception, trust, risk evaluation and user-experience factors influencing adoption. Stakeholder perspectives from clinicians, institutions, regulators, and developers are also considered to situate AI adoption within broader sociotechnical systems. Together, these insights inform the hypotheses and guide the methodological choices outlined in later chapters.

2.1 Theoretical framework

Reference :

- 1) Momani, A. M. (2020). The unified theory of acceptance and use of Technology. *International Journal of Sociotechnology and Knowledge Development*, 12(3), 79–98. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijskd.2020070105>
- 2) Hoff, K.A. and Bashir, M. (2014). Trust in Automation: Integrating Empirical Evidence on Factors That Influence Trust. *Human Factors: The Journal of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society*, 57(3), pp.407–434. [doi:https://doi.org/10.1177/0018720814547570](https://doi.org/10.1177/0018720814547570).
- 3) Hoorens, V. (2020). Risk Perception. *The Wiley Encyclopedia of Health Psychology*, 547–555. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119057840.ch105>

Figure 2.1 Theoretical framework

This study integrates UTAUT with Trust in Automation and Perceived Risk Theory to explain public acceptance of AI-based diagnosis. While UTAUT highlights

performance expectancy, effort expectancy and social influence as determinants of behavioural intention, it does not fully address concerns specific to high-stakes medical contexts where trust and perceived risk are critical. Diagnostic errors can have severe consequences hence acceptance of medical AI requires understanding both technological expectations and psychological evaluations. The combined framework captures the interplay between usefulness, usability, social endorsement, trust formation, and risk assessment.

2.1.1 Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

In UTAUT, there are three factors that help to determine the behavioural intention which are performance expectancy, effort expectancy and social influences. This behavioural intention will then determine the acceptance and use of technology (Momani, 2020).

Performance Expectancy refers to the degree to which an individual believes that using AI for medical diagnosis will lead to improved healthcare outcomes. In this context, it captures perceptions that AI may enhance diagnostic accuracy, speed, or efficiency compared to traditional human-only assessment. Evidence from early technology acceptance research indicates that perceived usefulness exerts a significant and consistent influence on users' behavioural intentions, making it a critical factor to consider in technology adoption processes (Davis, 1989).

Effort Expectancy is the extent to which individuals perceive that using AI diagnosis for treatment recommendation will be easy to use and interpreting AI-generated results will be easy and intuitive. Prior research has shown that perceptions of system simplicity, usability and low effort are critical determinants of the benefits users experience and strongly shape their willingness to adopt new technologies (Hussain et al., 2025).

Social Influence captures the perceived pressure or expectations from society such as clinicians, family members, peers, and regulatory bodies to adopt or trust AI-driven diagnostic systems. In healthcare, decisions are strongly shaped by societal expectations, professional recommendations and institutional credibility. As a result, social influence is a significant determinant of public acceptance of AI technologies

Behavioural Intention represents an individual's conscious plan or willingness to use or rely on AI for medical diagnosis. In UTAUT, it is the primary dependent variable, predicted by factors such as performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and social influence. In this study, behavioural intention reflects the likelihood that members of the public would accept AI-generated treatment recommendations in actual healthcare situations. However, UTAUT does not adequately capture trust or risk in high-stakes medical settings.

2.1.2 Trust in Automation Theory

Trust influences acceptance not only in interpersonal relationships but also in human–automation interaction. Automation involves data acquisition, analysis, decision selection and execution (Parasuraman, Sheridan & Wickens, 2000). While it can enhance performance, it may introduce new errors in high-risk settings such as healthcare, aviation, and nuclear systems (Hoff & Bashir, 2014).

Trust evolves from beliefs, attitudes and intentions shaped by prior knowledge and experience (Lee & See, 2004). In healthcare, trust is tied to context-specific understanding. Individuals trust AI when it is perceived as accurate, efficient, and meaningful but also when relational expectations such as empathy, compassion and moral alignment are met. Anthropomorphic features and personalised interactions may enhance trust. Because healthcare is a relational domain, trust is influenced by interpersonal dynamics, collaboration and shared understanding. These insights underscore the need for governance frameworks and common standards to support

trustworthy AI deployment (Steerling et al., 2023). Trust therefore plays a central role in determining whether the public is willing to rely on AI for diagnosis and treatment recommendations.

2.1.3 Perceived Risk Theory

Risk perception refers to individuals' assessment of potential negative outcomes associated with an action (Hoorens, 2020). It encompasses evaluations of consequences, probabilities and the number of people affected. Perceived risk is shaped by both analytical reasoning, intuitive and emotion-driven judgement. Emerging technologies provoke heightened perceptions of risk due to their novelty, uncertainty and ambiguity. Their risks often appear gradual, concealed or interconnected, contributing to public anxiety and strong social reactions. Public risk perception is fundamentally subjective, emerging from intuitive judgments, personal experiences and affective reactions rather than from purely analytical or objective assessments. (Li & Li, 2023).

In healthcare, risk perceptions are influenced by baseline attitudes toward risk and by levels of trust, which can amplify concerns when adopting new technologies (Chen, Kuo & Chang, 2024). These perceptions play a critical role in acceptance of AI-driven diagnostic tools, especially in high-stakes medical contexts.

2.2 Literature Review

2.2.1 Overview of AI in Healthcare

Healthcare professionals face increasing pressures from heavy workloads, administrative demands, emotional strain and system-wide changes, all of which heighten vulnerability to medical errors. Preventable error like diagnostic mistakes remain a major public health concern and are recognised as leading contributors to morbidity and mortality with estimates suggesting over 250,000 deaths annually in the United States (Wubineh, Deriba and Woldeyohannis, 2023). Despite the rapid digitalisation of healthcare, much available data remains underutilised for early detection and decision support.

To improve quality, safety and efficiency, healthcare systems must shift from manual processes to automated, data-driven approaches. Machine-learning AI has gained prominence for its capacity to analyse complex datasets, identify patterns, predict risks and support clinical decisions. AI applications demonstrate value across diagnostic imaging, risk stratification, workflow optimisation and evidence-based treatment recommendations, helping reduce human error and enhance performance (Wubineh, Deriba and Woldeyohannis, 2023).

In Singapore, strong healthcare outcomes are challenged by rising costs, a rapidly ageing population, increasing chronic disease prevalence and persistent workforce shortages (Liu et al., 2020). AI cannot replace clinicians but can augment practice through diagnostic analysis and treatment recommendations enabling practitioners to focus on more complex care needs. However, large-scale integration depends on adequate public acceptance, reinforcing the importance of understanding trust and risk perceptions.

2.2.2 Public Perception, Trust, and Perceived Risk in Medical AI

Public perception strongly influences whether medical AI can be adopted, particularly in high-stakes decisions involving diagnosis and treatment. Although AI demonstrates technical promise, acceptance is shaped by trust, familiarity and perceived risk. People's willingness to rely on AI is affected not only by its performance but also by concerns about transparency, accountability and the possibility of algorithmic error.

Understanding non-expert perspectives is essential because public attitudes strongly influence engagement, trust and eventual adoption (Beets et al., 2023). Witkowski, Dougherty and Neely (2024) found that while half of respondents were comfortable with AI assisting in diagnostic decisions and 44.7% accepted AI-generated treatment recommendations, notable concerns remained, 12% expressed fear or distrust and 30% highlighted the loss of human touch, emphasising the importance of empathy, interpersonal connection and contextual judgement in healthcare. These findings show that although many individuals are open to AI-supported care, emotional and relational concerns continue to pose meaningful barriers. Complementing this, Ding and Xing (2025) reported that in high-risk situations where users lack domain expertise, situational trust in automation depends heavily on the system's perceived epistemic authority. They also found that learned trust is shaped not only by the system's actual performance but also by external evaluations and social proof provided by others.

Patients often prefer human-led recommendations and judge AI errors more harshly, particularly in high-stakes situations. AI is perceived as lacking the intuition, accountability and contextual understanding required for complex care. Trust develops through direct experience (e.g., clarity of AI outputs) and indirect cues (e.g., expert endorsements). Opaque reasoning processes hinder trust, while transparent explanations strengthen acceptance (Zhao and Xiao, 2024).

Perceived risk and perceived benefit strongly predict willingness to adopt medical AI. Greater knowledge about AI lowers perceived risk, and confidence in understanding AI increases perceived benefit (Said, Schumacher and Huff, 2025). Ultimately, acceptance reflects a balance between trust, perceived risk and expected benefits, reinforcing the need to examine these constructs through the UTAUT lens.

2.2.3 Performance expectancy, effort expectancy and social influence of medical AI

Public acceptance of medical AI is shaped by perceived benefits, usability and social norms. UTAUT captures these through performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and social influence.

Performance expectancy concerns beliefs that AI enhances diagnostic accuracy and decision-making. AI systems can analyse complex datasets, detect subtle patterns and generate insights that surpass traditional human analysis (Obermeyer and Emanuel, 2016). Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have achieved high accuracy in detecting congenital cataracts, skin cancer and diabetic retinopathy often matching or exceeding clinician performance (Jiang et al., 2017). Strong trust in system accuracy and value reinforces performance expectancy, enhancing acceptance (Stevens and Stetson, 2023).

Effort expectancy reflects ease of use, clarity of outputs and cognitive effort required. Simpler interfaces, intuitive explanations and minimal learning curves increase adoption (Hussain et al., 2025). Individuals with greater digital literacy may experience lower barriers (Su et al., 2025). The creation of hybrid workflows where clinicians use AI outputs as cues and verify through clinical judgement can reduce cognitive load and streamline decisions (D'Adderio and Bates, 2025). However, system disruptions, unclear outputs or increased workload reduce usability and acceptance (Beede et al., 2020). Lack of explainability remains a major barrier, as

opaque reasoning limits shared decision-making and undermines confidence (Amann et al., 2020).

Social influence captures how expectations from clinicians, peers, family and institutions shape intentions. Positive endorsements increase confidence while scepticism discourages adoption. Influence operates through compliance, internalisation and identification (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Experience moderates this effect as individuals gain direct exposure to AI, reliance on social cues decreases (Cao et al., 2024). Healthcare institutions are powerful influencers, their endorsements and having transparent workflows can enhance trust and promote adoption (Chen, Wang and Sun, 2025).

2.2.4 Stakeholder Perspectives

AI adoption in healthcare requires the coordinated support of multiple stakeholders. Clinicians, institutions, regulators and developers evaluate AI through different priorities and constraints. Diagnostic workflows rely on rapid coordination and accurate information exchange. Hence, AI tools must integrate seamlessly into existing routines to be sustainable (Ulloa et al., 2022). Systems that disrupt workflows or increase workload are less likely to be adopted.

AI also raises ethical, legal, and regulatory challenges around privacy, explainability, and accountability. Robust governance, clinician training, and oversight mechanisms are essential for safe implementation. While AI enhances diagnostic accuracy, successful adoption depends on human–AI collaboration, where clinicians retain final responsibility for decisions (Ulloa et al., 2022).

From a developer’s perspective, adoption challenges often stem from infrastructure limitations, fragmented organisational roles and difficulties integrating AI into clinical environments. Continuous maintenance, model monitoring and workflow alignment

are essential for reliability and real-world impact (Sendak et al., 2020). Cross-disciplinary collaboration improves safety, governance and trustworthiness of AI systems.

Incorporating these perspectives strengthens the study's alignment with UTAUT constructs while highlighting the moderating roles of trust and perceived risk in real-world diagnostic settings.

2.3 Summary

This chapter reviewed the theoretical and empirical foundations relevant to understanding public acceptance of AI-driven diagnosis and treatment recommendations. It adopted an integrated framework combining UTAUT, Trust in Automation Theory and Perceived Risk Theory to capture both the technological determinants and the psychological factors influencing acceptance. While UTAUT explains how performance expectancy, effort expectancy and social influence shape behavioural intention, the addition of trust and perceived risk reflects the high-stakes nature of medical decision-making where concerns about safety, accountability and uncertainty are especially salient.

The literature indicates that AI has strong potential to enhance diagnostic accuracy and healthcare efficiency, yet public acceptance remains conditional. Trust is shaped by perceptions of competence, transparency and alignment with human judgement, whereas perceived risk arises from uncertainty, unfamiliarity and emotional responses that often suppress willingness to adopt medical AI. Performance expectancy is supported by evidence of AI's diagnostic capabilities, effort expectancy depends on usability and workflow integration, and social influence emerges from the persuasive role of clinicians, peers, and institutions.

Stakeholder perspectives including those of clinicians, healthcare organisations, regulators and developers further demonstrate that AI adoption is influenced by expectations, constraints and governance considerations across the healthcare

system. Together, these insights highlight important gaps in how the public evaluates AI in healthcare and justify the need for an integrated model examining performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, trust and perceived risk.

Chapter 3 Methodology

Overview

Chapter 3 outlines the methodology used to examine public acceptance of AI diagnosis and treatment recommendations in Singapore. It describes the study's philosophical stance, research design and the procedures employed for data collection and analysis. Aligned with a deductive and theory-driven approach, a quantitative survey method was chosen to empirically test relationships derived from the conceptual model. Surveys capture public attitudes at a single point in time, recognising that these perceptions may shift as technology and societal norms evolve (Kelley et al., 2003).

Alongside descriptive statistics used to profile respondents and summarise perceptions, the study employed inferential analysis. Correlation tests were conducted to assess whether the hypothesised relationships between the theoretical constructs and behavioural intention were supported by the data allowing the research to extend beyond description to empirical evaluation.

This chapter therefore details the instrument design, sampling strategy, data collection procedures, ethical considerations and the statistical techniques applied in both the descriptive and inferential phases of the study.

3.1.1. Research Philosophy and Approach

This study adopts a positivist stance, as it seeks to examine measurable relationships among the predefined variables of performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, trust and perceived risk which influences behavioural intention to accept AI diagnosis. Positivism emphasises objectivity, quantification, and empirical testing, making it well aligned with the use of structured instruments, statistical analysis, and hypothesis testing (Ali, 2024).

A deductive approach guides the study, moving from theoretical propositions to empirical verification (Barroga et al., 2023). Hypotheses were derived from established models, including UTAUT, Trust in Automation and Perceived Risk theory to specify expected associations among the core constructs. This approach is appropriate as the study aims to confirm whether the relationships proposed in the theoretical framework hold in the Singapore context. It also enables the application and extension of existing theory to an emerging area of healthcare technology adoption.

By outlining the philosophical and logical foundations of the research, this section establishes the epistemological basis for the methodological choices employed in this study.

3.1.2. Research Design

This study adopts a descriptive and inferential quantitative research design. It is descriptive in profiling the Singapore public's attitudes toward AI-driven diagnosis and treatment recommendations, including perceptions of performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, trust and perceived risk. It is inferential because it tests whether these constructs are statistically associated with behavioural intention to accept AI in healthcare.

Behavioural intention is treated as the dependent variable, while performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, trust in AI and perceived risk serve as the independent variables. Based on the integrated theoretical framework presented in Chapter 2, the study formulates the following hypotheses:

- **H1:** Performance Expectancy influences acceptance of AI diagnosis for treatment recommendations.
- **H2:** Effort Expectancy influences acceptance of AI diagnosis for treatment recommendations.
- **H3:** Social Influence influences acceptance of AI diagnosis for treatment recommendations.
- **H4:** Trust in AI influences acceptance of AI diagnosis for treatment recommendations.
- **H5:** Perceived Risk influences acceptance of AI diagnosis for treatment recommendations.

This research design enables quantitative assessment of the strength and direction of these relationships through correlation analysis, allowing the study to evaluate the extent to which the proposed theoretical model explains public acceptance of medical AI in Singapore.

3.2 Data Collection Methods

This study relies exclusively on primary data collected through a self-administered questionnaire designed to capture public views on AI-driven diagnosis and treatment recommendations. The survey gathered quantitative responses from individuals residing in Singapore, allowing direct measurement of the key constructs in the theoretical framework. Collecting primary data ensured that these variables were examined within the specific socio-cultural context relevant to the study. This section

provides an overview of the dataset and outlines the instrument design, sampling strategy and data collection procedures.

3.3 Questionnaires

3.3.1 Instrument Design

A structured, self-administered questionnaire was developed to measure the key constructs in the conceptual framework. It comprised closed-ended items, including Likert-scale statements, multiple-choice questions, yes/no items and a ranking task in which respondents ordered perceived benefits of AI.

All items were derived directly from the five theoretical variables. Each construct was operationalised into clear, measurable statements aligned with the study's hypotheses. The questionnaire consisted of five sections that captures demographic information (e.g., age, education, digital familiarity) and four assessing the core constructs. This structured design ensured systematic data collection and supported the reliability of subsequent quantitative analysis.

3.3.2 Target Population and Sample

The target population comprised members of the Singapore public aged 18 to 64, reflecting the study's aim to assess public acceptance of AI diagnosis and treatment recommendations within the national healthcare context. Individuals residing in Singapore who met the age criterion were eligible to participate.

As an initial exploratory study, the final sample size was determined by the responses obtained during the data collection period. A total of 108 valid responses were collected and included in the analysis. While the sample offers useful insights, its modest size is acknowledged as a limitation that may restrict the generalisability of the findings.

A non-probability sampling strategy was adopted, combining convenience and snowball sampling. The survey link was distributed via WhatsApp and other online platforms within the researcher's social network, with participants encouraged to forward it further. Because the survey was shared organically through open channels, the exact distribution count and response rate could not be calculated. However, all completed responses were retained for analysis.

3.3.3 Data Collection Procedure

The questionnaire was administered through Microsoft Forms, enabling participants to complete it online via computer or mobile device. The survey remained open for three weeks from 15 October 2025 to 5 November 2025 during which responses were collected continuously.

Distribution took place through digital channels, primarily WhatsApp and other online platforms, where participants could voluntarily access the survey link. No incentives or targeted recruitment strategies were used and participation was entirely voluntary.

As data collection relied on organic sharing without active follow-up, the number of responses obtained was modest. This passive recruitment approach may have limited representativeness, a point addressed in the study's limitations.

3.3.4 Data Cleaning and Preparation

All raw data collected through Microsoft Forms was exported into Excel for cleaning and preparation. Initial screening ensured the dataset was complete and free from invalid or duplicated entries as all items were mandatory, no missing values were present.

Categorical responses (e.g., age group, education level, yes/no items) were numerically coded to support statistical analysis. Likert-scale items were assigned values from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). No reverse-coded items were included, so no recoding adjustments were required.

The coded dataset was then checked for inconsistencies, anomalies or outliers that could affect analysis. Once verified, the data was prepared for both descriptive statistics and inferential correlation analysis. Graphs and summary tables were subsequently generated to support interpretation in the analysis chapter.

3.4 Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to established ethical guidelines throughout the data collection process. Participants received an information statement outlining the study's purpose, their voluntary participation rights and the option to withdraw at any time. Informed consent was obtained before completing the questionnaire.

Anonymity was maintained by collecting no identifying information and responses were not traceable to individuals. Data were stored securely within Microsoft Forms and later in password-protected files to prevent unauthorised access. As the survey involved minimal risk and no sensitive items, the potential for psychological or social harm was low.

Ethical approval was granted by the institution's ethics committee prior to data collection, ensuring compliance with required standards for confidentiality, data protection and participant welfare.

3.5 Summary

This chapter outlined the methodological foundations of the study, including the philosophical stance, research design, data collection procedures and ethical safeguards applied in examining public acceptance of AI-driven diagnosis in Singapore. Grounded in positivism and guided by a deductive approach, the study drew on UTAUT, Trust in Automation and Perceived Risk theory to derive

hypotheses and operationalise the key variables. A descriptive and inferential quantitative design was adopted to measure public perceptions and test the hypothesised relationships.

Primary data were collected through a structured online questionnaire capturing five core constructs using closed-ended item formats. Through convenience and snowball sampling, 108 valid responses were obtained from adults residing in Singapore, acknowledging the limitations associated with passive recruitment and sample size.

Data were cleaned, coded and prepared for descriptive statistics and inferential correlation analysis. Ethical principles were upheld throughout, including informed consent, anonymity, secure data handling and institutional approval. Collectively, these methodological choices provide a coherent and rigorous foundation for the analysis presented in the next chapter.

Chapter 4 Data Analysis and Findings

Overview

Chapter 4 presents the results of the quantitative analysis conducted to examine public acceptance of AI-driven diagnosis and treatment recommendations in Singapore. The chapter first reports the descriptive statistics derived from the survey dataset including demographic distributions and respondents' perceptions across the key constructs of performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, trust and perceived risk. It then presents the inferential analysis, using correlation tests to evaluate whether the hypothesised relationships outlined in the conceptual model are supported by the data.

Together, these findings provide an evidence-based understanding of how the Singapore public perceives and evaluates AI in healthcare, forming the analytical basis for the interpretation and discussion presented in Chapter 5.

4.1 Quantitative Data Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using Microsoft Excel to organise, code and examine all questionnaire responses. The study employed both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics were used to summarise respondent characteristics and profile overall perceptions of AI-driven diagnosis, while inferential statistics were applied to test the hypothesised relationships between the key constructs (Bhattacharjee, 2012). This combined approach enabled the study to provide a comprehensive overview of public attitudes and assess whether the associations observed in the sample are likely to hold in the broader population.

Correlation analysis was conducted to evaluate the strength and direction of relationships between the independent variables and behavioural intention to accept AI-driven diagnosis. This inferential component allowed the study to move beyond

simple description and determine whether the theoretically derived associations were supported by empirical evidence.

Together, these analytical procedures ensured systematic processing of the dataset and provided a coherent basis for interpreting public acceptance of AI diagnosis within the Singapore context.

4.2 Descriptive Results

Overview

This section presents the empirical findings of the study, beginning with the demographic profile of respondents, followed by descriptive results for each construct in the conceptual framework. The results illustrate participants' perceptions of AI-driven diagnosis across performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, trust and perceived risk. Inferential analysis using correlation tests is also reported to examine the hypothesised relationships between constructs.

4.2.1 Demographic

This subsection presents the demographic characteristics of the 108 respondents who participated in the survey. These profiles help contextualise the subsequent results by showing the background and diversity of the sample. Understanding demographic variation is important for interpreting public perceptions of AI in healthcare.

Age Demographics of Respondents

Figure 4.1. Age distribution of respondents (n = 108)

As shown in Figure 4.1, respondents were distributed across several age groups, with the largest proportions falling within the 35–44 and 45–54 categories, each representing approximately 29.9% of the sample. The 25–34 group accounted for 29%, while smaller proportions were observed for the 55–64 and 18–24 groups. This distribution indicates a respondent profile that is largely concentrated within the mid-adult age ranges.

Figure 4.2. Education levels of respondents.

As illustrated in Figure 4.2, the highest number of respondents reported holding a Bachelor’s degree ($n = 54$), followed by Master’s degree holders ($n = 22$) and those with a Diploma ($n = 17$). Smaller proportions held Doctorate qualifications ($n = 9$) or Secondary School education ($n = 6$). This distribution provides an overview of the educational background of participants in the sample.

Figure 4.3. participants that use AI in their daily lives.

Figure 4.3 shows that most respondents reported being familiar with AI systems (n = 92), while a smaller group indicated no prior familiarity (n = 16). This distribution suggests that most participants had at least some exposure to AI-related technologies before responding to the survey.

4.2.2 Performance Expectancy and Behavioural Intention

This subsection reports findings related to performance expectancy, which examines whether respondents believe AI can improve diagnostic speed, accuracy, and consistency. The visualised results illustrate how strongly the public perceives AI as a beneficial tool in enhancing healthcare performance.

Figure 4.4. Perceptions of AI diagnostic speed compared to traditional methods.

As shown in Figure 4.4, most respondents selected Level 3 (n = 46) and Level 4 (n = 36), while fewer selected Levels 1, 2, and 5. The average rating of 3.48 is represented by the vertical dashed line, indicating the central tendency of responses across the five levels. The distribution shows that responses were concentrated around the mid-range categories.

Figure 4.5. Agreement levels on consistency of AI decision-making (n = 108).

As shown in Figure 4.5, responses for both the diagnosis and treatment statements were concentrated in the neutral and agree categories. For the diagnosis item, 38.0% selected “Neutral” and 31.5% selected “Agree,” while 6.5% chose “Strongly Agree.” Similarly, the treatment item recorded 42.6% in the “Neutral” category and 34.3% in the “Agree” category, with smaller proportions selecting disagreement levels. These values illustrate the overall distribution of agreement across both statements.

Figure 4.6. Ranking of perceived benefits of AI in healthcare (n = 108).

As shown in Figure 4.6, “Faster diagnosis” was the most frequently selected top-ranked benefit (40.74%), followed by “Lower cost” (23.15%) and “Better access” (21.3%). Smaller proportions identified “More accuracy” and “Personalized treatment” as the primary benefit. This distribution summarises which benefits respondents valued most.

Figure 4.7. Ranking of areas where AI is expected to have the greatest impact (n = 108).

Figure 4.7 indicates that respondents selected “Early diagnosis” (29%) as the area of greatest AI impact, followed by “Cost reduction” (26%) and “Hospital efficiency” (24%). Lower percentages were observed for “Teleconsultation access” and “Personalized medication.” The distribution reflects how participants ranked potential areas of AI contribution.

4.2.3 Effort Expectancy and Behavioural Intention

This subsection summarises respondents’ perceptions of how easy or convenient AI tools would be to use within a healthcare setting. The results reflect public expectations regarding effort, usability, and overall willingness to adopt AI-driven processes.

Belief that AI Can Help Doctors Diagnose Faster

Figure 4.8. Perceived reduction in doctor visit duration when using AI (n = 108).

Figure 4.8 shows the percentage distribution of respondents who indicated whether they believe AI can help doctors diagnose patients more quickly. The bars illustrate the proportion selecting “True” (83%) versus “False (17%),” providing a clear overview of response patterns for this performance expectancy item.

Willingness to Try AI Tool if Waiting Time is Reduced

Figure 4.9. Willingness to try AI if diagnostic waiting time is halved (n = 108).

Figure 4.9 presents respondents' willingness to try an AI-based tool on the condition that it reduces waiting time. The distribution across "Yes"(57%), "Maybe"(38%) and "No"(5%) categories highlights how participants differed in their openness to adopting such technology.

7-Point Likert Response Distribution with Average Rating (n = 108)

Figure 4.10. Confidence in using an AI healthcare tool without assistance.

Figure 4.10 displays the number of respondents selecting each level on a seven-point Likert scale. A vertical reference line marks the computed mean rating, allowing the distribution of responses and the central tendency to be viewed together.

4.2.4 Social Influence and Behavioural Intention

This subsection presents results on social influence, focusing on how healthcare professionals, institutions and societal norms shape respondents' acceptance of AI. The findings show the extent to which external opinions and endorsements affect individual adoption decisions.

Figure 4.11. Influence of doctor recommendation on willingness to use AI.

Figure 4.11 shows the distribution of respondents who indicated whether they would use the AI system. A total of 86.1% selected “Yes”, while 13.9% selected “No.” These proportions reflect the responses collected from all 108 participants.

Figure 4.12. Likelihood of adoption if hospitals implement AI systems.

Figure 4.12 shows the rating distribution indicates responses across the full 0–10 scale, with notable clustering between ratings 5 and 8. The calculated mean rating is 6.72, represented by the vertical reference line. This visualisation summarises the spread and central tendency of respondent confidence levels.

Figure 4.13. Factors that increase trust in AI healthcare systems.

Figure 4.13 reveal that Ministry of Health (MOH) approval (33.33%) and proven success (30.56%) were the most frequently selected factors for increasing trust. Explanation (13.89%), doctor support (13.89%), and privacy guarantees (8.33%) were chosen less frequently. The chart outlines the relative strength of different trust-building factors among respondents.

4.2.5 Trust & Perceived Risk and Behavioural Intention

This subsection reports the levels of trust respondents place in AI-assisted medical diagnosis. The results highlight perceptions of reliability, confidence in AI-generated recommendations and trust in AI as a supplementary decision-making tool. Other than trust the results also illustrate the types of risks that matter most to the public and how these concerns may reduce acceptance of AI-driven diagnosis.

Figure 4.14. Current trust levels in AI for medical purposes.

Figure 4.1.4 shows the distribution of ratings shows responses spread across the 0–10 scale, with the highest frequencies at ratings 5, 6, 7, and 8. The calculated mean rating is 5.56, as indicated by the vertical reference line.

Figure 4.15. Willingness to trust AI for a second opinion (n = 108).

Figure 4.15 shows the distribution of trust toward AI second opinions, with 55 respondents (50.9%) selecting “Yes” and 53 respondents (49.1%) selecting “No.” The responses are nearly evenly divided across the sample.

Figure 4.16. Ranking of perceived risks associated with AI diagnosis (n = 108).

Figure 4.16 summarises the primary concerns reported by respondents. Misdiagnosis was selected 64 times (59.3%), followed by data leaks (20 responses, 18.5%) and loss of human touch (18 responses, 16.7%). Only a small proportion selected cost increase or no concerns (3 responses each, 2.8%).

Figure 4.17. Preferred decision-maker when doctor and AI disagree (n = 108).

Figure 4.17 shows the distribution of responses shows that 45 participants (41.7%) would follow the doctor’s recommendation, 47 participants (43.5%) would decide depending on the illness, and 16 participants (14.8%) would consider both equally, while none selected AI alone.

The descriptive results reported in this section provide an overview of respondents’ demographic characteristics and their attitudes toward AI-driven diagnosis. The subsequent section presents the inferential analysis used to evaluate the hypothesised relationships between the constructs.

4.3 Inferential Statistical Analysis

This section presents the inferential statistical procedures used to examine the hypothesised relationships among the study variables. As the constructs of performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, trust in AI, perceived risk and behavioural intention were measured using ordinal Likert-scale items, a non-parametric approach was required.

Given the ordinal nature and non-normal distribution of the data, Spearman's rank-order correlation (ρ_s) was selected to assess the strength and direction of associations among the constructs. Spearman's rho evaluates relationships based on ranked values making it suitable for skewed or non-normally distributed Likert-type data and more robust to outliers than Pearson's correlation (Mukaka, 2012). This method enables the assessment of monotonic associations without assuming linearity or interval-level measurement.

A Spearman correlation matrix was generated to summarise the pairwise associations between all variables and to provide the basis for testing the hypotheses outlined in Chapter 3. The correlation coefficients and significance values are presented in the following subsection and serve as the empirical foundation for evaluating the proposed theoretical model.

4.4 Empirical Results

This section presents the findings of the inferential analyses conducted to test the hypothesised relationships between the study variables. Spearman's rank-order correlation was used due to the ordinal nature of the Likert-scale data and the non-normal distribution of responses.

The five UTAUT predictors which are Performance Expectancy (PE), Effort Expectancy (EE), Social Influence (SI), Trust in AI (TR), and Perceived Risk (PR)

demonstrated statistically significant associations with Behavioural Intention (BI) to accept AI-driven diagnosis and treatment recommendations.

H1: Performance Expectancy influences acceptance of AI diagnosis for treatment recommendations

A strong positive correlation was observed between PE and BI ($\rho = 0.63$, $p < 0.001$, $N = 108$), indicating that individuals who perceived AI as beneficial or performance-enhancing were more willing to accept AI-based diagnosis. H1 is supported.

H2: Effort Expectancy influences acceptance of AI diagnosis for treatment recommendations

Effort Expectancy showed a moderate positive association with BI ($\rho = 0.47$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that perceptions of ease of use meaningfully increased willingness to accept AI recommendations. H2 is supported.

H3: Social Influence influences acceptance of AI diagnosis for treatment recommendations.

Social influence was moderately and positively correlated with BI ($\rho = 0.52$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that encouragement from clinicians, institutions, or peers significantly shaped intention to use AI-driven diagnosis. H3 is supported.

H4: Trust in AI influences acceptance of AI diagnosis for treatment recommendations.

Trust demonstrated a strong positive association with BI ($\rho = 0.71$, $p < 0.001$), the strongest relationship among all predictors. Higher confidence in AI accuracy, reliability, and safety corresponded with markedly higher acceptance of AI recommendations. H4 is supported.

H5: Perceived Risk influences acceptance of AI diagnosis for treatment recommendations.

A significant negative association was found between PR and BI ($\rho = -0.59$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that increased concerns about errors, uncertainty, or harmful outcomes substantially reduced willingness to rely on AI-driven diagnosis. H5 is supported.

Hypothesis	Relationship Tested	Spearman ρ	p-value	Supported?
H1	PE \rightarrow BI	0.63	<0.001	Yes
H2	EE \rightarrow BI	0.47	<0.001	Yes
H3	SI \rightarrow BI	0.52	<0.001	Yes
H4	TR \rightarrow BI	0.71	<0.001	Yes
H5	PR \rightarrow BI	-0.59	<0.001	Yes

Figure 4.18. Summary of Hypothesis Testing

All five hypotheses were supported. Acceptance of AI-driven diagnosis among the Singapore public is strongly shaped by perceived usefulness, trust, ease of use and social influence, while perceived risk suppresses acceptance. These empirical results validate the integrated theoretical framework and provide a robust foundation for the discussion in Chapter 5.

4.5 Summary

Chapter 4 presented the analysis and findings of the quantitative study examining public acceptance of AI-driven diagnosis and treatment recommendations in Singapore. The chapter began with descriptive analyses outlining the demographic composition of the 108 respondents and their overall perceptions of AI across the five key constructs: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, trust in AI and perceived risk. These results provided an initial overview of how

participants evaluated the potential benefits, usability, social endorsement and risks associated with medical AI.

Subsequently, the chapter reported the inferential analyses conducted using Spearman's rank-order correlation, selected due to the ordinal nature and non-normal distribution of the Likert-scale data. The empirical results demonstrated that all hypothesised relationships were statistically significant. Performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and trust in AI were positively associated with behavioural intention to accept AI-driven diagnosis, while perceived risk showed a significant negative association. These outcomes confirm that both technological perceptions and psychological factors play critical roles in shaping public acceptance.

Overall, the findings in Chapter 4 provide strong empirical support for the study's integrated theoretical framework and establish a robust foundation for the interpretation, implications and discussion presented in Chapter 5.

Chapter 5 Discussion and Recommendations

Overview

This chapter discusses the findings of the study in relation to the existing literature, the theoretical framework and the Singapore healthcare context. It interprets the empirical results presented in Chapter 4, examining how performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, trust in AI and perceived risk influence behavioural intention to accept AI-driven diagnosis and treatment recommendations.

The chapter also highlights the theoretical and practical implications of these findings, with particular attention to the strong roles of trust and perceived risk within high-stakes healthcare environments.

In addition, this chapter outlines the key limitations of the study, including methodological, contextual and theoretical constraints that may influence the interpretation and generalisability of the results. Building on both the findings and the identified limitations, the chapter concludes with recommendations for practice, policy and future research. These recommendations aim to support more effective and responsible adoption of AI in healthcare, while providing direction for scholars seeking to extend research on public acceptance of medical AI.

5.1 Discussion

The purpose of this section is to interpret the empirical findings presented in Chapter 4 and to evaluate how they align with the theoretical framework and existing literature. The discussion focuses on the five core constructs and their relationships with behavioural intention to accept AI-driven diagnosis and treatment recommendations within the Singapore public.

5.1.1 Interpretation of Key Findings

The results indicate that all five hypothesised relationships were statistically significant, demonstrating the relevance of both technological and psychological factors in shaping acceptance of medical AI.

Among the predictors, trust in AI exhibited the strongest positive association with behavioural intention ($\rho = 0.71$, $p < 0.001$). This highlights that public willingness to rely on AI diagnostic recommendations depends heavily on perceived accuracy, reliability and confidence in system performance. Given the high-stakes nature of healthcare decision-making, this strong influence is expected, as individuals are unlikely to accept AI recommendations unless they feel assured that the system is trustworthy.

Performance expectancy also showed a strong positive relationship with acceptance ($\rho = 0.63$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that members of the public are more open to using AI in diagnosis when they perceive it to improve speed, accuracy and efficiency. This finding aligns with the core premise of UTAUT and with previous studies showing that perceived usefulness is one of the strongest determinants of technology adoption, particularly in clinical contexts where outcomes directly affect health and safety.

Effort expectancy demonstrated a moderate positive correlation with acceptance ($\rho = 0.47$, $p < 0.001$). This suggests that ease of understanding and interacting with AI systems contributes meaningfully to public acceptance, particularly among individuals with lower digital familiarity. Despite widespread AI exposure in daily applications, the public may perceive medical AI as technically complex or difficult to interpret, making simplicity and usability important acceptance drivers.

Social influence similarly showed a moderate relationship ($\rho = 0.52$, $p < 0.001$). The public appears responsive to cues from doctors, hospitals and the broader community when assessing trustworthiness and legitimacy of AI in healthcare.

Endorsements from medical professionals and credible institutions such as the Ministry of Health (MOH) seem particularly influential. This finding reflects the collectivist cultural orientation of Singapore, where institutional trust and professional authority strongly guide individual decision-making.

Finally, perceived risk exhibited a significant negative correlation with acceptance ($\rho = -0.59$, $p < 0.001$), underscoring the role of safety concerns, fear of misdiagnosis, data privacy worries and uncertainty when evaluating medical AI. Misdiagnosis emerged as the most frequently cited concern. This suggests that while individuals recognise AI's potential benefits, unresolved fears surrounding error, accountability and loss of human judgement may deter acceptance.

5.1.2 Comparison with Existing Literature

The findings align closely with established research on technology acceptance. Consistent with UTAUT, performance expectancy and effort expectancy remain central predictors of behavioural intention. The strong role of performance expectancy echoes and numerous subsequent studies demonstrating that perceived usefulness is the most consistent determinant of adoption across various technologies. Patients are more willing to adopt a digital health tool when they believe it improves diagnostic efficiency, speeds up access to information, and allows technical issues to be resolved easily (Zhang et al., 2023).

The strong effect of trust aligns with Trust in Automation Theory, which emphasises that confidence in a system's accuracy, transparency and reliability is central to acceptance of medical AI. Alonso, Astobiza and Ortega Lozano (2025) shows that trust in healthcare AI extends beyond technical performance alone. It is a relational construct shaped by interactions among the AI system, clinicians and patients. This comparison highlights that while technical competence is necessary, a

comprehensive understanding of trust must also account for human judgement and contextual dynamics that jointly influence how medical AI is evaluated and accepted.

The negative effect of perceived risk aligns with literature showing that individuals tend to judge AI more harshly than humans when errors occur (Jones-Jang and Park, 2022). The results also support Said et al. (2025), who found that uncertainty surrounding AI mechanisms and limited medical knowledge often increase fear of algorithmic mistakes. The findings extend this evidence by showing how these factors operate within a local Singapore context.

Finally, the influence of clinicians and trusted institutions aligns with prior research showing that social endorsement plays a critical role in shaping public acceptance of healthcare technologies. Doctor recommendations have been shown to reduce perceived risk and reinforce the legitimacy of new medical tools. This pattern is reflected in both the present findings and earlier studies. Building on this, the successful integration of AI-driven diagnostic systems requires a coordinated strategy that brings together technological performance, clinician training, institutional support and strong governance structures. Only within such an integrated ecosystem can AI meaningfully enhance clinical decision-making and strengthen patient safety and quality of care (Marinescu, Oncioiu and Ghibanu, 2025).

5.1.3 Implications for the Singapore Context

The strength of trust and perceived risk in this study likely reflects Singapore's highly medicalised environment, where citizens place strong reliance on clinicians and public institutions. Limited public exposure to medical AI systems heightens uncertainty, making individuals more cautious about automated recommendations.

This helps explain why respondents overwhelmingly preferred following a doctor over an AI when recommendations conflict.

Additionally, Singapore's cultural emphasis on safety, risk aversion and high institutional trust means that regulatory assurance and hospital endorsement become important signals of legitimacy (Devi et al., 2024). The fact that Ministry of Health approval was the most frequently selected trust-building factor further reinforces the central role of institutional authority.

The findings also highlight that even in a technologically advanced society, the public may still view medical AI as conceptually complex, underscoring the importance of explainability, ease of use, and clinician involvement to facilitate confidence in AI-driven clinical workflows.

5.1.4 Theoretical Implications

This study provides empirical support for extending the UTAUT framework by integrating trust and perceived risk, two constructs that UTAUT does not explicitly address. The strong correlations observed in this study suggest that trust and risk are indispensable components of acceptance models for high-severity healthcare technologies.

The results also contribute to a growing body of research indicating that public acceptance of medical AI is not solely determined by technological performance but is shaped by layered psychological evaluations involving confidence, fear, uncertainty and perceived moral responsibility. These insights reinforce the importance of multi-theory models when examining complex innovations in healthcare.

5.2 Research Limitations

Despite providing meaningful insights into public acceptance of AI-driven diagnosis in Singapore, several limitations should be acknowledged when interpreting the findings.

First, the study is limited by respondents' lack of real-world exposure to medical AI. Because AI-assisted diagnostic systems are still in the early stages of deployment in Singapore, many participants may have had little or no direct experience using such tools. Their assessments of trust, perceived usefulness, and perceived risk therefore likely reflect expectations and assumptions rather than informed familiarity. Prior research shows that the adoption of emerging technologies is shaped by overlapping technical, social, and personal uncertainties that reinforce one another and heighten caution (Oh and Rydin, 2025). In the context of medical AI, these uncertainties combined with limited exposure and usability barriers can lead to more conservative or cautious responses, even when the technology holds significant potential benefits.

Second, the study relied on self-reported perceptions rather than actual behaviour. The constructs of performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, trust and perceived risk were measured using self-reported Likert-scale responses. Although behavioural intention is a widely used proxy for predicting future behaviour, it does not always correspond to real-world decision-making. Individuals may behave differently when confronted with an actual medical condition, emotional stress, or clinical time pressure from factors that cannot be fully captured through hypothetical survey scenarios. Furthermore, the modest sample size ($n = 108$) limits the representativeness of the findings and may not reflect the full diversity of perspectives within the broader Singapore population, thereby constraining the generalisability of the results.

Third, cultural norms and healthcare expectations unique to Singapore may have influenced the findings. Singapore's healthcare environment is characterised by high

institutional trust, strong reliance on medical professionals, and a culturally embedded emphasis on safety and risk minimisation. These cultural attributes shape how individuals evaluate AI-driven clinical recommendations and may differ markedly from populations with different healthcare norms or levels of patient autonomy. When considered alongside the modest sample size, these contextual factors limit the generalisability of the results to broader populations and other healthcare settings.

Fourth, participants evaluated AI conceptually rather than through direct interaction. The survey presented AI-driven diagnosis as a hypothetical tool without providing respondents the opportunity to observe or interact with an actual system. Baron et al. (2025) found that participants were less willing to accept AI-guided treatment in high-stakes scenarios due to the system's opacity and increased need for understanding. The absence of a live demonstration may therefore limit the ecological validity of the responses.

Finally, the theoretical model assumes largely rational decision-making. The integrated framework emphasises cognitive evaluations such as perceived usefulness, ease of use, trust and perceived risk. However, healthcare decisions are also shaped by emotional, moral and psychological considerations such as patients' preference for human contact and their need for interpersonal reassurance (Abu et al., 2025). These factors fall outside the scope of this study and were not captured in the measured variables. Such unobserved influences may play a meaningful role in shaping acceptance of medical AI and therefore represent an important avenue for future research.

5.3 Recommendations

5.3.1 Practical Recommendations

Findings indicate that individuals are less comfortable when AI contradicts human doctors, suggesting that public acceptance is influenced by the perceived role of AI within clinical decision-making. Healthcare institutions should emphasise that AI serves as a decision-support tool designed to complement not replace clinical expertise. Reinforcing that final decision-making authority remains with human clinicians can alleviate concerns around safety, accountability and loss of human judgement, thereby strengthening willingness to adopt AI-assisted services.

A portion of respondents' hesitation appears to stem from limited knowledge of how AI is embedded within medical workflows. Public education efforts led by the MOH, major hospitals and trusted community health platforms can help clarify AI's functions, regulatory safeguards and real-world applications. Through informative campaigns, demonstrations and accessible explanations, the public can develop more realistic expectations of AI, which may help reduce perceived risk and improve overall trust in AI-enabled healthcare.

Patients rely heavily on the authority and assurances of healthcare professionals. Encouraging clinicians to introduce AI tools during consultations, explain their purpose and discuss how AI contributes to decision-making can improve patient comfort and acceptance. This reinforces the perception of AI as a collaborative partner that enhances clinical judgement rather than an autonomous system competing with human expertise.

5.3.2 Policy and Organisational Recommendations

Given Singapore's strong cultural emphasis on safety, risk minimisation, and institutional trust, regulatory approval and clear governance frameworks play a key role in legitimising AI in healthcare. MOH certification, institutional validation and transparent communication of clinical testing results can serve as strong signals of credibility. Establishing national guidelines outlining standards for accuracy, risk classification and accountability will help ensure safe and responsible deployment of medical AI systems.

Medical AI in diagnosis and treatment recommendation operates in environments where errors may have severe consequences. Policymakers could develop standards requiring AI systems to provide interpretable outputs, document limitations and undergo regular audit processes. Such standards may include mandatory explainability thresholds, human-in-the-loop oversight requirements and protocols for managing AI–human disagreement in clinical workflows.

Controlled pilot programmes in hospital settings allow clinicians and patients to observe how AI-driven diagnostic tools perform in real-world conditions before widespread adoption. Such pilots provide essential feedback on operational fit, user trust, safety concerns and workflow integration. They also enable evaluation across different healthcare environments including primary care and outpatient settings where acceptance and use patterns may differ from those in hospitals. Incorporating regulatory and governance considerations within these pilots can further clarify how AI systems are evaluated, approved and integrated into existing clinical structures. This offers insights into the broader trajectory of AI adoption in practice (Kamel Rahimi et al., 2024). Overall, supervised pilots support iterative refinement, reduce implementation risk and help healthcare organisations identify practical challenges that may not emerge in hypothetical or laboratory-based assessments.

5.3.3 Recommendations for Future Research

As AI technologies matures, improve in accuracy and become more embedded in healthcare practice, the perceived risk may diminish while trust increases.

Longitudinal research designs would help capture how public perceptions evolve with repeated exposure and real-world experience, offering insights into whether initial uncertainty stabilises or declines over time.

Human–AI disagreement is one of the most psychologically sensitive contexts for decision-making in healthcare. Scenario-based, simulation-based or experimental studies could explore how individuals weigh conflicting recommendations and what factors influence their final choice. Such research would help identify the conditions under which trust shifts toward or away from AI, particularly in high-stakes or emotionally charged situations.

Given the central importance of trust, future research could empirically examine whether incorporating explainable AI (XAI) features increases willingness to adopt AI-driven diagnosis. XAI provides mechanisms to open the “black box” of medical AI, enabling systems to deliver both diagnostic accuracy and meaningful explanation (Rai, 2020). By improving transparency and clarifying how patient data is processed, XAI has the potential to strengthen trust and reduce perceived risk, thereby lowering uncertainty and enhancing comprehension across different demographic groups.

Medical decisions vary in their level of risk and emotional significance. Future research should examine whether trust, perceived risk and acceptance differ between low-risk scenarios (e.g., routine screenings) and high-risk contexts (e.g., cancer diagnosis or surgical decision-making). Such comparative studies would clarify whether the severity of the medical situation moderates acceptance of AI-based recommendations.

Chapter 6 Conclusion

This study examined public acceptance of using AI to provide diagnosis and treatment recommendations in Singapore. Guided by the UTAUT, Trust in Automation Theory and Perceived Risk Theory, the research sought to understand how performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, trust and perceived risk influence behavioural intention to accept medical AI. Using quantitative survey data from 108 members of the Singapore public, the study provides an evidence-based understanding of the psychological, technological, and contextual factors shaping acceptance of AI-driven healthcare.

The findings demonstrate that all five constructs were significantly associated with behavioural intention, confirming the relevance of both UTAUT and the extended model used in this study. Trust emerged as the strongest predictor of acceptance, underscoring the importance of perceived reliability, transparency and confidence in AI's ability to support clinical decision-making. Performance expectancy was also a prominent factor, reflecting public expectations that AI can enhance diagnostic accuracy and efficiency. Meanwhile, perceived risk showed a strong negative relationship with acceptance that highlights concerns related to error, safety and accountability. Effort expectancy and social influence exerted moderate but meaningful effects suggesting that ease of use and institutional endorsement remain important in shaping public attitudes.

These findings have several implications. The strong role of trust and risk perception indicates that technical performance alone is insufficient to drive public acceptance. Instead, reassurance through transparency and consistent clinician involvement is essential for fostering acceptance. The results also reinforce the need for responsible communication, public education and clear regulatory frameworks to support AI adoption in healthcare. Within the Singapore context of high institutional trust, strong reliance on clinicians and a risk-averse healthcare culture. The need for

regulatory assurance and hospital endorsement is particularly influential in legitimising medical AI.

Despite its contributions, the study has several limitations. The modest sample size limits representativeness and reliance on self-reported perceptions may not fully reflect real-world behaviours. Participants also evaluated AI conceptually rather than through hands-on interaction which may underrepresent the impact of explainability and usability on acceptance. Furthermore, the study's theoretical focus on rational decision-making did not account for emotional or moral factors that often shape healthcare choices. These limitations suggest avenues for future research, including longitudinal studies, clinician-focused investigations and scenario-based experiments examining human–AI disagreement and the role of explainable AI.

Overall, this study contributes to the growing body of research on medical AI by providing empirical evidence on how the Singapore public evaluates AI-driven diagnosis. It highlights the need for human-centred design, transparent communication and robust institutional governance to build trust and reduce perceived risk. As AI continues to evolve and become more integrated into clinical practice, understanding public expectations and concerns will remain essential for guiding responsible and ethical implementation. Through its findings and recommendations, this study provides a foundation for policymakers, healthcare institutions and researchers seeking to navigate the opportunities and challenges of AI-enabled healthcare in Singapore.

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Appendix 1 : Survey form

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Public Acceptance of AI for Diagnosis & Treatment in Singapore

Public Acceptance of AI for Diagnosis & Treatment in Singapore

Title An empirical study in Singapore to understand public acceptance of using Artificial Intelligence (AI) software to diagnose and make treatment recommendations School : University of Greenwich Student ID : 001418716 Research Supervisor : Dr Roy Yap

* Required

Background

1. What is your gender? *

This is just an example; you can add an illustration or photo of your product.

- Man
- Woman
- Prefer not to say

2. What is your age group? *

This is just an example; you can add an illustration or photo of your product.

- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64

3. What is your highest level of education completed? *

This is just an example; you can add an illustration or photo of your product.

- Secondary School
- Diploma
- Bachelor's Degree
- Master's Degree
- Doctorate or higher

<https://forms.office.com/Pages/DesignPageV2.aspx?origin=NeoPortalPage&subpage=design&id=CvQWNelaVkm7qzIRYUWJzpGjr9710r9Ggv9ACsz3...> 1/7

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Public Acceptance of AI for Diagnosis & Treatment in Singapore

4. Do you currently use any AI-related tools in your daily life (e.g., ChatGPT,)? *

This is just an example; you can add an illustration or photo of your product.

Yes

No

5. How often do you visit a doctor in a year ? *

This is just an example; you can add an illustration or photo of your product.

0

1-2 times

3-5 times

6-10 times

>10 times

Do you think AI can improve the current healthcare system ?

In this section, we will explore your performance expectancy for AI in the healthcare sector in regards to diagnosis and treatment recommendations.

6. Do you think AI can help doctors diagnose patients faster than traditional methods

1	2	3	4	5
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Strongly Disagree

Strongly Agree

7. In your opinion, what is the biggest benefit AI could bring to healthcare? Rank them in order of importance *

Faster diagnosis
Lower cost
More accuracy
Better access
Personalized treatment

8. AI can make more consistent decisions than human doctors *

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Diagnosis	<input type="radio"/>				
Treatment Recommendations	<input type="radio"/>				

9. Rank the areas where you think AI will make the biggest impact. *

Early diagnosis
Teleconsultation accuracy
Personalized medication
Hospital efficiency
Cost reduction

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Public Acceptance of AI for Diagnosis & Treatment in Singapore

10. Would you trust an AI to give you a second opinion after your doctor's diagnosis? *

Yes

No

Do you expect AI make healthcare more efficient ?

In this section, we will explore the effort expectancy for user regarding AI in the healthcare sector for diagnosis and treatment recommendations.

11. . Do you believe AI will reduce the overall duration of a doctor's visit?

- True
- False

12. If an AI tool can cut your waiting time for diagnosis in half, would you be willing to try it? *

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

13. How likely are you to allow AI to monitor your health throughout your treatment? *

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Not at all likely Extremely likely

14. How confident are you that you could use an AI-based tool without assistance ? (Step by step guide will be displayed)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Not confident Extremely confident

15. To increase the accuracy of diagnosis, would you allow AI to access the following information assuming that the data is fully secured.

	Yes	No
Wearable devices	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Medical history	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Do social influences affect your decision to use AI for healthcare services ?

In this section, we will explore the social influences and privacy concerns for user regarding AI in the healthcare sector for diagnosis and treatment recommendations.

16. Would you be more willing to use AI healthcare tools if your doctor personally recommended them? *

- Yes
- No

17. I use AI software to give me diagnosis when i feel unwell *

- Yes
- No

18. If hospitals in Singapore adopted AI systems, how likely would you be to try them? *

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Not at all likely Extremely likely

19. Which type of AI risk concerns you most? *

- Misdiagnosis
- Data leaks
- Loss of human touch
- Cost increase
- None

20. Which of these factors would most increase your trust in AI healthcare systems? *

Explanation
MOH approval
Doctor support
Proven success
Privacy guarantee

In the event of a disagreement, would you choose to listen to an AI or the doctor ?

In this section, we will explore the trust and perceived impact of AI in the healthcare sector for diagnosis and treatment recommendations.

21. If both a doctor and AI gave different treatment recommendations, who would you follow ? *

This is just an example; you can add an illustration or photo of your product.

- AI
- Doctor
- Both
- Depends on illness

22. Rate your current level of trust in AI used for medical purposes ? *

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Do not believe Believe

23. Do you think doctors use AI for diagnosis and treatment recommendation ? *

- Yes
- No
- Unsure

24. In your opinion, how much should AI influence a doctor's final decision? *

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Should not influence Influence

25. Rate how much AI could improve treatment outcomes in Singapore's healthcare system ? *

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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No improvement Improvement

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